

ROADMAP

Rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems in the management of animal production

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ROADMAP Mid-term report on stakeholder consultations

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About the ROADMAP research project

The overall aim of ROADMAP is to **foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains.** ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

AMR is recognized as a significant threat to global public health and food security. Overuse and improper use of AMs in many parts of the world contribute to the emergence and spread of AMR. Although human and animal health require AMs, it has been estimated that two thirds of the future AMU growth worldwide will be in animal production. Improving the management of AMU in farm animals is therefore a critical component of dealing with AMR and optimizing production in the livestock sector. Nevertheless, the variety of contexts of AMU in the livestock sector is a major challenge to managing AMR. **There is no “one-size-fits-all” solution to improve AMU and strategies must be contextually developed** (for instance, strategies used in the Danish pig industry are difficult to adapt and adopt in the French free-range poultry farming). Successful solutions must be combined and tailored to the production systems and the social and economic context in which they operate.

ROADMAP will meet three general objectives, in line with the EU AMR Action plan:

- i)** Rethink AM decision-systems and animal health management;
- ii)** Develop options for encouraging prudent AMU in animal production;
- iii)** Engage all actors in the food and drug supply chains in fostering a more prudent use of AMs.

Project consortium

Part . N°	Participant organisation name (acronym)	Country
1	Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement (INRAE) **	France
2	Association de coordination technique agricole (ACTA) ***	France
3	Centre de coopération internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement (CIRAD) **	France
4	University of Liverpool (ULIV) *	United Kingdom
5	Cardiff University (CU) *	United Kingdom
6	James Hutton Institute (HUT) **	United Kingdom
7	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna (UNIBO) *	Italy
8	Aarhus Universitet (AU) *	Denmark
9	Eigen Vermogen van het Instituut voor Landbouw en Visserijonderzoek (EV-ILVO) **	Belgium
10	Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (FiBL) **	Switzerland
11	Stichting Wageningen Research (WR) *	Netherlands
12	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU) *	Sweden
13	Southern Agriculture and Horticulture Organization (ZLTO) ***	Netherlands
14	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders (EFFAB) ****	Netherlands
15	Fundacion Empresa Universidad Gallega (FEUGA) ****	Spain
16	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen (DGZ) ***	Belgium
17	INRA Transfert (IT) ****	France

* Universities/veterinary schools

** Research institutes specialized in both fundamental and applied agricultural and veterinary sciences

*** Public and private advisory services Organisations

**** Knowledge transfer and Innovation organisations

ROADMAP Guidelines for Recruitment of Stakeholders

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ACTA	Association de Coordination Technique Agricole
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
AMs	Antimicrobials
AMU	Antimicrobial use
ANIS-EMA	AU Epidemiology and Management research unit
AU	Aarhus Universitet
AU-ANIS	AU Department of Animal Science
CA	Consortium Agreement
CIRAD	Centre de cooperation internationale en recherche agronomique pour le développement
CLs	County leaders
COGECA	General Committee for Agricultural Cooperation in the European Union
COPA	Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations
CU	Cardiff University
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
DGZ	Dierengezondheidszorg Vlaanderen VZW
DISTAL	Department of Agricultural and Food Science
DLS	Department of Livestock Sciences
DMP	Data Management Plan
EAAP	European Federation of Animal Science
EC	European Commission
EFFAB	European Forum of Farm Animal Breeders
EIP-AGRI	The Agricultural European Innovation Partnership
EU	European Union
EV-ILVO	Eigen vermogen van het instituut voor landbouw en visserijonderzoek
ExCom	Executive Committee
FABRE-TP	Farm Animal Breeding and Reproduction Technology Platform
FEUGA	Fundacion empresa Universidad Gallega
FiBL	Forschungsinstitut für biologischen landbau stiftung
FSL	Food Safety Lab
FVE	Federation of Veterinarians of Europe
HUT	The James Hutton Institute
ICOH	International Conference on One Health
INRA	Institut national de la recherche agronomique
IPR	Intellectual property rights
IPUDC	Intellectual Property Use and Dissemination Committee

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IT	INRA Transfert
ITAs	Technical Agricultural Institutes
MAA	Multi Actor Approach
MS	Milestone
NGOs	Non-governmental organisations
ODP	Outreach & Dissemination Plan
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
RSCs	Regional Stakeholder Communities
SAB	Stakeholder advisory board
SLU	Sveriges Lantbruksuniversitet
UEVP	Union of European Veterinary Practitioners
ULIV	The University of Liverpool
UNIBO	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna
WBVR	Wageningen Bioveterinary Research
WLR	Wageningen UR Livestock Research
WOHC	World One Health Congress
WP	Work Package
WPLs	Work Package Leaders
WR	Stichting Wageningen Research
WVAC	World Veterinary Association Congress
ZLTO	Zuidelijke land- en tuinbouworganisatie vereniging

1 Summary

ROADMAP is a multi-actor approach (MAA) research project, which means that project partners must have complementary types of knowledge from research and practice. This document presents a protocol for the creation of a stakeholder’s community, how they will be engaged and what kind of stakeholders’ knowledge is needed to reach the goals set, where and when those stakeholders are going to be involved.

2 Introduction

This Mid-term report on stakeholder consultations was delayed because of the COVID impact, which made that most of the stakeholder activities had to be planned online.

Task T7.1 entitled “Stakeholders community creation and management” is conducted as a part of WP7 “Strategic communication, dissemination & exploitation”. Stakeholders’ community creation and management is described in the ROADMAP Grant Agreement through different actions.

D7.1 “ROADMAP guidelines for recruitment of stakeholders” presented the methodological basis for the creation of the stakeholders’ community. It is an easy-to-use guideline document for the recruitment of stakeholders and devoted to the partners to use it. One partner per ROADMAP country is in charge of engaging the stakeholders at regional/national level. A specific section of the [ROADMAP project website](#) gives visibility to the ROADMAP stakeholders’ community. Deliverable D7.5 shows the improvement of the project’s stakeholder engagement.

3 The stakeholders’ community

The ROADMAP stakeholders’ community is formed by different stakeholders as described in D7.1:

Table 1: Description of the RSCs stakeholder categories

	CATEGORY	DESCRIPTION
1.	Practitioners (animal health professionals):	people who are expected to implement the solutions proposed in field: farmers, veterinarians, technical advisors and farmer’s organizations.
2.	Private partners:	small and medium enterprises (SME’s) linked to the activity, like breeding and feeding industries, pharmaceutical companies, retailers and processors.
3.	Multipliers:	sector and professional associations, NGO’s, EIP-AGRI operational groups from the specific country, regional or national agricultural project partners and networks and other public or private initiatives relevant for the agricultural sector.
4.	Researchers:	researcher groups from universities or technological centres which offer knowledge about agricultural. They have to be able to share their experience and knowledge within the RSCs.
5.	Policy-makers and administration:	public authorities from different policy areas who can foster new politics, regulations or means to empower the sector.

Most of them are reached by the country leaders in their case studies or living labs activities as well as by communication team through project’s social media networks, website and events.

3.1 Stakeholders' communication channels

3.1.1 Website

From M18 December 2020 until 08 March 2022, the official ROADMAP project website www.roadmap-h2020.eu got 10,158 views with an average time on page up to two minutes.

Overview

Figure 1 Website overview

Pages more visited were **home**, and **news** section as it is showed in the next figure.

Figure 2 Website pages

Audience

Figure 3 Website audience

The most used languages were English, French and Italian.

Language	Users	% Users
1. en-us	2,016	54.05%
2. en-gb	299	8.02%
3. fr-fr	260	6.97%
4. it-it	196	5.25%
5. fr	170	4.56%
6. es-es	107	2.87%
7. nl-nl	67	1.80%
8. da-dk	50	1.34%
9. de	47	1.26%
10. es	43	1.15%

Figure 4 Website visitors' language

3.1.1.1 Country pages

To communicate directly in the native languages of stakeholders, the ROADMAP project decided to create country pages, with content developed by country leaders for their communities to increase engagement. At the moment this deliverable is written, 7 regional pages were published and are open to all visitors and 3 are private (2 for Belgian pigs and calves living labs members and 1 more for Danish living lab members) in local languages:

COUNTRY PAGES

Would you like to follow the news on the ROADMAP project in your own language? Select the country below to see more!

Figure 5 Country Pages published

The partners EFFAB and FEUGA managed together with country leaders the creation of regional pages to be linked on the project website. The guidelines were created and shared with country leaders on the ROADMAP collaborative platform, as well as by mail and presented at different meetings as ExCom, and in one-to-one meetings with country leaders. EFFAB is in charge of the access protocol and FEUGA is responsible of the content or design, in case partners need help.

Figure 6 Guidelines for Regional stakeholder pages

Each country page is different as country leaders are free to select the content they want to share within their regional community.

Figure 7 Regional stakeholders pages by country published

- Other countries such as Belgium decided to maintain private pages with limited access to each of their living labs, and included their confidential information as minutes, presentations, results. The UK and Vietnam are still pending to create regional pages, while the Swiss page is almost ready to be published.

To increase the engagement of these pages, several posts were created on social networks:

Figure 8 Posts published about regional pages

3.1.1.2 SAB page

Also, a private page under the ROADMAP official website was created for SAB members. All presentations and discussions, minutes and notes are accessible by restricted access only for SAB members.

Table 2: Stakeholder Advisory Board members

Organisation	Group
FEFAC	Feed
IFAH Animal Health Europe	Animal Health
Star-Idaz	Animal Health
FESASS Fédération Européenne pour la Santé Animale et la Sécurité Sanitaire	Breeding
FVE previous director (retired late 2020)	Vets
OIE	Animal Health/Policy maker
One Health EJP	Animal Health
ENOLL	Animal Health
EFFAB	Breeding

Figure 9 SAB page

3.1.1.3 Subscription form at website by Mailchimp

A subscription form was created and linked to the website to facilitate stakeholder’s registration.

By 9 March 2022, the audience reached 102 contacts, 98 of these are subscribers. 9 from Belgium, 1 from Brazil, 7 from Denmark, 1 from Finland, 20 from France, 4 from Germany, 2 from India, 8 from Ireland, 11 from Italy, 2 from Mozambique, 5 from Netherlands, 2 from Spain, 3 from Sweden, 4 from Switzerland, 13 UK, 2 Vietnam, 1 USA, 1 Uganda and 1 from Nigeria.

Figure 10 ROADMAP subscribers map

ROADMAP Mailing List

Subscribe to ROADMAP mailing list to receive updates and progress on our project.

Email Address

First Name

Last Name

Company/Organisation

Country

Figure 11 ROADMAP website form

3.1.2 Social networks

3.1.2.1 Facebook

Figure 12 ROADMAP Facebook page

ROADMAP Facebook page is being followed by 47 people and reached 37 likes.

Our Facebook reach is the number of unique users who saw our post or page, regardless of whether they engaged with it. So, if you make a post and 100 people look at it, your reach is 100 people. Facebook reach is always measured within a specified period, and this metric was analysed from December 2020 to March 2022.

Content most interesting for visitors were EAAP Conference (September) and ¿Te interesa la reducción (August) with 583 and 493 respectively.

Figure 13 ROADMAP Facebook results

The second step was to rate these proposals also between partners. A poll was created for that also on Mentimeter and results are shown in the image below:

Figure 16 ROADMAP partners final decision

This decision was shared also with the DISARM project so that they proceed with the same internal approach with their partners and come up with 3 final names. When the two proposals would be ready, we will ask stakeholders to vote between these 6 final names in order to involved them also at this level.

3.1.2.2 Twitter

Figure 17 ROADMAP twitter account

ROADMAP Twitter account has 240 followers, follows 316 external accounts and shared 285 posts. Most followers are animal health professionals, such as veterinarians and microbiologists. Also researchers, and academia follow ROADMAP Twitter.

3.1.2.3 LinkedIn

Figure 18 ROADMAP LinkedIn account

LinkedIn account is being followed by 171 mainly from Spain, France, Belgium, Italy, United Kingdom, Netherlands and Switzerland.

Figure 19 ROADMAP LinkedIn follower demographics

Figure 20 ROADMAP LinkedIn followers map

Visitors’ top job functions are related to Program and project management, Research, Education, Community and Social Services or Healthcare Services.

Figure 21 LinkedIn visitor demographics

Figure 22 ROADMAP LinkedIn followers job position

3.1.2.4 Youtube

ROADMAP YouTube channel has 6 subscribers, 7 videos and a total of 668 views of all videos until 8 March 2022.

Figure 23 ROADMAP YouTube channel

Figure 24 ROADMAP YouTube channel analytics

ROADMAP stakeholders were also closely involved at case study and living labs levels:

3.2 Case study level

In the various case studies, interviews with vets and farmers are conducted within the framework of WP2. The participants were selected according to the research questions that drive this WP and through the method of snow-ball sampling and the principle of data saturation: representativeness is achieved when variation amongst certain criteria that matters for the research is obtained. The main criteria are age, gender, sectors, and farming systems (for farmers) and business models (for vets). The selection also follows GDPR rules to ensure data confidentiality and avoid conflict of interests.

Figure 25 Farmer and vets interviews

Figure 26 Farmer surveys

Figure 27 Vets surveys

Table 3: Number of farmer interviews by country

Country	Number of farmer interviews
Vietnam	11 farmers, 11 pharma companies
Belgium	2 farmers
Denmark	13 farmers
France	18 farmers (broilers)
UK	32 calf rearers
Italy	7 poultry farmers, 5 pig farmers
Mozambique	80 farmers plus 10 technicians

Table 4 Number of farmer surveys

Country	Number of responses
Belgium	0
France	64
Italy	8
Netherlands	8
UK	43
Spain	18
Sweden	6
Switzerland	45

Table 5: Vets interviews

Country	Number of interviews
Belgium	8 pig vets and 3 veal calves vets
Denmark	16 cattle vets
France	32 pig and poultry vets ; 18 dairy vets
Italy	2 pig vets
UK	12 vets
Sweden	21 dairy vets and 5 poultry vets

Table 6 Vets surveys

Country	Number of responses
Belgium	0
Denmark	138
France	139
Italy	138
Netherlands	19
UK	112
Spain	47
Sweden	76
Switzerland	16

3.3 Living labs level

Table 7: Final list Living labs with coordinators and stakeholder representing

Living Lab	Coordinators and facilitators	Stakeholders representing
Belgian pigs Belgian veal	Erwin Wauters, ILVO Stefaan Ribbens, DGZ	Different farmer Unions, veterinary practitioners, Animal Health Care Services, Federal agency of the Safety of the Food chain, Federal Agency for medicines and health products, Expertise Center for Antimicrobial Usage and Resistance, Academic Research centers and universities, pharmaceutical companies, Centre for Agro-and fisheries marketing, National Federation of slaughterhouses, cutting plants and wholesalers, retailers, National feed association, feed and nutrition companies, Sector guide organisations for primary production, Agricultural research, innovation and information centers, Department of Agriculture and Fisheries, Belgian Veal Calve Association
Danish pigs	Hanne Kongsted, ICROFS Line Kollerup, AU Merete Studnitz, ICROFS	Producers, extension services, vets, industry (R&D, extension, export consultant), slaughterhouses, researcher, retailer

Danish dairy (cows and calves)	Line Kollerup, AU Mette Vaarst, AU	Veterinary practice and advisory service, university education of vets and ag scientists, The Danish Vet. Society, 3 companies involved in the dairy or calf sectors (a dairy company with conventional and organic milk, a meat trading company and a company for calf feed and equipment), The Agricultural Advisory Service Centre, SEGES, under the Danish Agricultural Agency (the Danish farming sector's organization)
Dutch poultry (turkeys)	Fleur Hoorweg, WR Annick Spaans, ZLTO Heleen Prinsen, ZLTO Anne Marie Rebel, WR	Veterinary practice, Animal Health service, 3 farmers board members of the branch organisation (AVINED), branch organisation (AVINED), Dutch farmers organization, Feed organization, Wageningen University and research.
French poultry & pigs	Catherine Belloc, ONIRIS Nantes Mathilde Paul, ENVT Christian Ducrot, INRAE,	French Ministry of Agriculture, Veterinary practitioners (pig and poultry sectors), Interprofessional councils (INAPORC for pig and ANVOL for poultry), development institutes (IFIP for pig and ITAVI for poultry)
French dairy	Eleonore Pommier, Idele Manon Fuselier, Idele Mathilde Paul, ENVT Marlene Guiadeur, Idele Aurore D. Wache, Idele	(LL not started yet, so here are the stakeholders we would like to invite): farmers, veterinarians, milk industries, federation of health protection groups, French livestock advisors
Italian poultry	Massimo Canali, UNIBO Frederique Pascali, UNIBO Caetano Luiz Beber, UNIBO	French Ministry of Agriculture, Veterinary practitioners (pig and poultry sectors), Interprofessional councils (INAPORC for pig and ANVOL for poultry), development institutes (IFIP for pig and ITAVI for poultry)
Italian pigs	Massimo Canali, UNIBO Paolo Trevisi; UNIBO Roberta Ruggeri, UNIBO Costanza Romanelli, UNIBO	Work in progress
Swiss pigs	Barbara Früh, FiBL Bernadette Oehen, FiBL Mirjam Holinger, FiBL	Animal welfare organization, Slaughterhouse / meat production company, Organic farmers association, Veterinary university, Livestock traders, Farmers, Association of Swiss organic pig farmers, Pig health service, Organic research institution, Organic certification body

Swiss veal	Michael Walkenhorst, FiBL Bernadette Oehen, FiBL	Vets, Advisory service (veterinary: Swiss calf health service), organic producer organization (Bio Suisse), veterinary and socio-economic researcher (FiBL), Swiss organic farmers (dairy, beef and veal).
UK calves	Orla Shortall, HUT Claire Hardy, HUT Lee-Ann Sutherland, HUT Carol Kyle, HUT Gareth Enticott, CU Kieran O'Mahony, CU	Farm technicians involved in calf care (Calf-carers / rearers). In addition, based on the development in the LL, a wider group of stakeholders will be invited e.g. consultancies, milk buyers, milk companies, Woman in Dairy-group.

At Living Labs level, stakeholders were purposively selected based on initial stakeholder mapping through interviews. The objective was to respect the multistakeholder-approach and be relevant for the purpose and focus of each Living Lab. In the Deliverable report D4.1, we provided the guidelines as given below. The Living Labs always have the possibility to involve and include new stakeholders, when the need is identified.

When inviting stakeholders to participate in Living Labs, it has been and still is a challenge for some teams to deal with competing companies, and the choice had to be made to cover and focus on the problem area of the ROADMAP project, and the context has been evaluated and taken into account. However, many stakeholders have also potentially conflicting interests in relation to development of the farming sector involving animals (e.g. conflicts between low prices for animal products versus animal welfare concerns), and we consider it a potentially important function of the Living Lab to facilitate processes that bring stakeholders together and can change conflicts of interest to commonalities of interest, when it comes to overall societal concerns, such as antimicrobial resistance, through facilitation and dialogues in the Living Labs by creating rooms of confidence and confidentiality.

Guidelines given in Deliverable Report 4.1 regarding selection of stakeholders for the Living Labs:

It is absolutely fundamental that Living Labs (LL) take a multi-stakeholder approach (Figure 2), and the group of participants or ‘stakeholders’ is heterogeneous and positioned differently in relation to a given issue or problem. Stakeholders may include for example, academics, industry representatives, citizens, public agencies, non-profit organisations, consultants, advisors, entrepreneurs, public authorities, universities, various institutions, end-users, and companies (Almirall and Wareham 2011; Bergvall-Kåreborn et al. 2009; Feurstein et al., 2008; Veeckman et al 2013).

Figure 28 Groups of actors in a LL according to Kris Steen 2017.

Usually, a LL will include public-private-citizen partnership (Dube et al, 2014). The set-up of a LL needs to represent actors who have experience, knowledge and interest in the focus area and the questions of a LL, and who can contribute to co-creation. According to Westerlund and Leminen (2011), there are four main groups of actors who need to be represented in a LL (see Table 2). In other words, it has to be carefully considered who should be invited to participate, both as representatives for certain groups or categories of actors, but also as individuals with personal experience and backgrounds which could be of potential importance for the co-creation process.

In the Living Lab Methodology Handbook (U4LoT, 2019) it is suggested to consider the following points:

- Participation should be voluntary
- Maximization of diversity among categories of users/actors including public actors (Zavratnik et al, 2019).
- Involve users who are flexible, open for change and have a strong social competence
- Socio-demographic variation in gender, age or education (respective to the context)

During the research process, new stakeholders may be identified that are relevant for inclusion (U4LoT, 2019). On the other hand, stakeholders who do not bring any added value to the living lab should stop their participation (Petruska and Kovacs 2016).

3.3.1 Living labs impact on stakeholders

By March 2022, the impacted stakeholders by Living labs processes reached at least 146 stakeholders, the following figures show the concrete stakeholders profiles impacted such as: farmers; veterinarians; cooperatives, integrators and food industries; pharma, breeding or feed mills companies; public actors; researchers; consumers and associations, and farm advisors.

Figure 29 Total Stakeholders involved in the Living Labs

Figure 31 Stakeholders involved in the Swiss Living Lab

Figure 30 Stakeholders involved in the UK Living Lab

Figure 33 Stakeholders involved in the Dutch Living Lab

Figure 32 Stakeholders involved in the Italian Living Lab

Figure 35 Stakeholders involved in the French Living Lab

Figure 34 Stakeholders involved in the Danish Living Lab

3.4 Events

Also, the ROADMAP project was introduced by partners at a series of events :

Table 8 events where ROADMAP project was introduced

PARTICIPATORY ACTIVITIES			
partner	location	title	date
INRAE/INRAE Transfer	Paris (France)	KOM	18-19/06/2019
INRAE	Brussels (Belgium)	Fitter Livestock Farming Workshop	06/11/2019
INRAE	Brussels (Belgium)	EU- Canadian workshop	4-5/02/2020
EFFAB	Online	EFFAB Annual General Meeting	28 May 2020
INRAE/INRAE Transfer	Online	Second Annual Meeting	20- 22 April 2021
Joint Project Event(ROADMAP, AVANT, HealthyLivestock and DISARM)	Online	5th International Conference on Responsible Use of Antibiotics in Animals	7-9/06/2021
Joint Project Event (ROADMAP, AVANT, HealthyLivestock and DISARM)	Online	Fighting AMR in animals: experiences and progress from the field	24/11/2021
CIRAD, ENVT	Online	One Health Antimicrobial Stewardship Conference	March 2021
UNIBO	Edinburgh	6th World One Health Congress in Edinburgh	2020
EV ILVO	Online	EPRUMA meeting	15 December 2021

EFFAB	Online	FAO-IAEA Event International Symposium on Sustainable Animal Production and Health	28 June -02 July 2021
AU	Davos, Switzerland	EAAP 2021	August/September 2021
Nicolas Fortane/INRAE	Podcast online	Cordis podcast	18 November 2021
FEUGA	Spain	First Stakeholder's Forum at EUGreenweek	9th and 10th of June 2021
	Spain	Second Stakeholder's forum at Galicia Innovation Days	27/10/2021
UNIBO	Italia	LL meeting on Italian poultry sector	17 December 2021
AU	Denmark	Living Lab meetings	
EV ILVO	Belfast	SVEMP 2022 conference	23-25 March 2022
UNIBO	Kuala Lumpur	ISESSAH 2021	17-18 Nov. 2021

4 Surveys to vets and farmers

Under WP2, consultations to vets and farmers are ongoing at regional level. To promote this activity, a section on the ROADMAP website was created ([Surveys \(roadmap-h2020.eu\)](http://Surveys.roadmap-h2020.eu)). A video with a text was translated into all project languages to share the surveys on social networks and by email with interesting multipliers, and to engage stakeholders at their language of origin. In addition, a social media campaign has been actively carried out in national languages by tagging and mentioning relevant national and international institutions on Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook accounts of the ROADMAP project.

Figure 36 ROADMAP surveys website section

The key message translated into all project languages was:

Are you a farmer or a veterinarian involved in animal production? Help us to better understand animal health practices and identify transition pathways towards prudent use of antibiotics in the livestock sector. Select the option best suits you!!

Partners were also asked to tag or mention multipliers through the different social networks to reach and engage regional stakeholders.

5 Message house

During the online 3rd ROADMAP General Assembly on 22-24 February 2022, the WP7 team held an interactive session on “message house” activity focused on the case studies in each country. Message houses are an effective communication tool to create simple messages targeting different stakeholder groups. During the session, a total of 10 breakout rooms were created based on each country (France, Denmark, Sweden, The Netherlands, UK, Belgium, Italy, Switzerland, Vietnam and Mozambique). Each country leader, partners, SAB members and guests were totally free to move through the different breakout rooms to co-create and discuss:

- The **main objective** of the case studies based on the country, taking into account the target audience or different levels (farm, industry, regulatory and societal levels) and their expectations – also based on the problem trees
- Summarizing the **work and the strategies** of the case studies in each country in 1-2 sentences
- **Core messages and expected impact** of the case study results and strategies on the **target audience** or different levels
- **Deliverables and milestones** supporting the core strategies

After an introduction to the activity, the breakout rooms were created at regional level and discussion began. The next figure shows some results from the co-creation results. At the end of the breakout room activity, moderators shared results with all participants. This activity will help the WP7 team to see differences between regions in terms of objectives, expected impacts per stakeholder’s profile and expected results.

Figure 37 ROADMAP general example provided

Figure 38 ROADMAP message houses results per region

WP7 will use these results to extract some materials that we can use to disseminate. For instance, the outcomes of these message house activity will be used as an input while creating infographics per each country.

This matrix will be covered by partners including all stakeholders engaged and complemented with a stakeholder table like the one following:

Key Stakeholder Data Sheet

Personal information	
Last name	
First name	
Role	
Mobile	
Email	
Internal	
Organisation	
Dept / Unit	
External	
Company	
Address	

Communication preference						
Frequency	Face-Face	Text	Email	EXCOM	GA	Other
Daily						
Weekly						
Bi-monthly						
Monthly						
Crisis						

Concerns and needs

Involvement during phases			
Phase	Value	Low	High
Initiating			
Planning			
Executing			
Closing			

Influence

Topic	Value
Power/Influence	
Interest	

Motivation to move towards AMR	
Level	Level
High	
Medium	
Low	

Details

7 CONCLUSION

While ROADMAP stakeholder engagement strategy following the multi-actor approach was introduced in the D7.1 report, this current deliverable analyses the progress made, the communication channels used, the regional pages created, the events organised during this period, and also the message house activity carried out per region with SAB members and external participants/stakeholders.

Due to the COVID situation, the involved countries have been impacted by different restrictions and this also affected the engagement of stakeholders. More effort should be carried on and more interactive activities should be proposed for online channels where face-to-face stakeholder meetings cannot be possible.